

AIRSHIP

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Deliverable 9.4

Dissemination, exploitation and communication report

WP9 Dissemination, outreach and roadmapping

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	5
2	Impact of the dissemination, exploitation and communication	6
3	Dissemination	6
3.1	Publications	6
3.2	Events	7
3.3	Clustering.....	8
3.4	Dissemination results and next steps	8
4	Exploitation	9
4.1	First exploitation workshop	9
4.2	Exploitation results and next steps	10
5	Communication.....	10
5.1	Project image.....	10
5.2	Website.....	11
5.2.1	Structure	11
5.2.2	Consortium Input	12
5.2.3	Results	12
5.2.4	Planned updated	13
5.3	Social Media	13
5.3.1	X.....	13
5.3.2	Linkedin	13
5.3.3	Planned strategy for social media	14
5.4	Communication materials	14
5.4.1	Graphic materials	14
5.4.2	Newsletters	15
5.4.3	Videos.....	15
5.5	Other communication activities	15
5.5.1	Press conference and press releases.....	16
5.5.2	Communication events and initiatives	16
5.6	Communication results.....	16

List of Tables

Table 1. Abbreviation and Acronyms	3
Table 2 List of publications by M24.....	6
Table 3 Events where AIRSHIP has been/ will be presented	7
Table 4 KPIs for dissemination	8
Table 5 Communiation Key Performance Indicators.....	17

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Photos of AIRSHIP in ILA Berlin 2024	7
Figure 2 Projects and initiatives that have joined the AIRSHIP clustering events by M24	8
Figure 3 Example of a Unique Value Proposition template.....	9
Figure 4 AIRSHIP logo - version 1	10
Figure 5 AIRSHIP logo - version 2	10
Figure 6 Main page of the AIRSHIP webpage (www.airshipproject.eu)	11
Figure 7 AIRSHIP's website menu dropdown	12
Figure 8 AIRSHIP's X best performing post and general analytics	13
Figure 10 AIRSHIP's LinkedIn and X followers demographics breakdown	14
Figure 9 AIRSHIP's LinkedIn analytics	14
Figure 11 AIRSHIP's posters versions 1, 2 and 3.....	14
Figure 12 Pictures of the CIAG joint press conference.....	16
Figure 13 AIRSHIP in the EU Corner of the European Researchers Night of the Macaronesia.....	16

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
M	Month
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

Table 1. Abbreviation and Acronyms

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 9.4 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication report showcases the results up to Month 24 of the AIRSHIP project dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy. Month 24 marks the midway point of the project.

This report provides an opportunity to review the communication and dissemination activities undertaken, facilitating the evaluation of the performance and reach of the actions planned in *Deliverable 9.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan with Communication activities*.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a rundown of the communication, exploitation and dissemination activities in the AIRSHIP project for the first half of the project. AIRSHIP aims to revolutionize inter-island and inland water transport through the development of Wing-In-Ground autonomous ekranoplanes. As such, increasing visibility and promoting the results of the outcomes and technologies developed is crucial to the success and uptake of the findings and innovations during and after the lifetime of the project.

Work Package 9 is called *Dissemination, outreach and roadmapping* and consists of three complimentary tasks: *9.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan and activities*, *9.2 Stakeholder analysis and clustering* and *9.3 Innovation strategy and roadmapping*. The present report is encased within task 9.1 and is preceded by *Deliverable 9.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan with Communication activities* and *Deliverable 9.2 Stakeholder analysis* and will be followed by *Deliverable 9.3 Clustering activities*, an update of this Deliverable in month 48 (end of the project) and *Deliverable 9.5 Innovation agenda and roadmap*.

As stated in *Deliverable 9.1*, the main goals of the task are implementing strategies in communication –raising awareness to a larger audience-, dissemination –informing stakeholders of the project outputs and seeking synergies with related EU-funded projects- and exploitation –knowledge transfer and use of the results towards the commercialisation of the project-. During this project period the actions have focused on communication and have kickstarted the dissemination as results and knowledge were developed, as such the present report will focus on the results of dissemination and communication and will set up the roadmap for the exploitation.

The structure of D9.4 will follow the same as D9.1 and will evaluate the results against the expected Key Performance Indicators set in the Grant Agreement.

2 Impact of the dissemination, exploitation and communication

In line with the communication guidelines for Horizon Europe funded projects, the main goals of the AIRSHIP project's outreach actions are to raise awareness of the results of the project, seek synergies and ensure the use of all key exploitable results of the project.

In the first period of the project, the actions have focused on the set-up of the communication and dissemination channels, in creating a recognisable project brand and in setting up the stakeholders' networks necessary for the exploitation of the project. As such, in this deliverable we will review the impact, understanding that the second part of the project is the expected time for the utilization of the tools, networks and plans solidified up to this point.

Impact is to be measured both by the consecution of the Key Performance Indicators set out in the Grant Agreement, as well as by the relevance of results for the project's exploitation phase.

3 Dissemination

Dissemination in AIRSHIP is understood as sharing results with people who can best make use of them and, as such, the tools (logo, poster, etc.) and channels (social media, website) by which the dissemination activities are maximised will be expanded on in the communication section. For the purpose of this deliverable, dissemination is mainly carried out through publications, attendance and organisation of events and clustering efforts. The target audience for dissemination is set to be research communities, industry and policymakers.

3.1 Publications

At the mid-point of the project, M24, the consortium has focused on the publication of the results mainly tied to the results of *WP2 Environmental footprint sustainability and social impact*. The table below is an overview of the published peer-reviewed papers and those pending decision:

Table 2 List of publications by M24

Title	Authors	Status
Decarbonizing City Water Traffic: Case of Comparing Electric and Diesel-Powered Ferries	<i>R. Otsason, U. Tapaninen</i>	Published
Business Opportunities for a Ground Effect Vehicle - Case of Canary Islands	<i>R. Otsason, O.-P. Hilmola, U. Tapaninen, B. Tovar</i>	Published
Perspectives of using Wing in Ground vehicles in the Gulf of Finland from the Safe Navigation Aspect	<i>P.-R. Jännes</i>	Pending
Masters' thesis: Deployment of unmanned wing-in-ground vehicles - legal aspects	<i>K. Kerem</i>	Pending

3.2 Events

The project is very active in attending relevant events and has even been invited to high-level dissemination events such as the ILA Berlin 2024. These appearances are highly relevant and have a proven impact in our target audiences, as evidenced by the multiple contacts achieved at the occasions, as well as the intensification of the social media engagement and website visits.

Figure 1 - Photos of AIRSHIP in ILA Berlin 2024

The table below shows the scientific and technological events where AIRSHIP has been presented at this point of the project (in a darker shade), as well as the planned events for the upcoming year:

Table 3 Events where AIRSHIP has been/ will be presented

Event	Dates
European Maritime Day. Brest.	24, 25 May 2023
Jornadas de Robótica y Bioingeniería. Madrid.	14, 15 June 2023
Transport Research Arena. Dublin.	15 – 18 April 2024
ILA Berlin 2024. Berlin.	5-9 June 2024
FinDrones. Oulu.	6, 7 November 2024
ROBOT 2024 Conference. Madrid.	6-8 November 2024
HE Conference. Oviedo.	28 November 2024
Waterborne Days 2025. Brussels.	4, 5 February 2025
European Maritime Day 2025. Cork.	21,23 May 2025
HSBO Forum 2025. Gothenburg.	3-5 June 2025
TransNav 2025. Gdansk.	11-13 June 2025
Futures Conference. Turku.	10-12 June 2025
55 th Paris Airshow. Paris.	16-22 June 2025

3.3 Clustering

Even though the clustering actions for the project are encased within *Task 9.2 - Stakeholder analysis and clustering*, the efforts in liaising and collaborating with the cluster projects and initiatives is a key aspect of the project’s dissemination. As such, a short rundown of the activities carried out up to this point is explained here.

AIRSHIP aims to organise at least three online clustering events, but, after the clustering efforts started and the *Deliverable 9.2 – Stakeholders Analysis* was presented, the dissemination leaders decided to extend the cluster events to four in order to fully develop the actions planned (described in D9.2) and to be able to cover all interested projects and initiatives.

At M24, two online cluster events have been organised counting with the presence of 11 projects/initiatives. Nonetheless, probably the most relevant synergy set up at this point is the adhesion to the Aviation Twin Transition Cluster organised by the RefMap project, which will start in January 2025 and counts with highly relevant stakeholders. It is planned to have the final cluster event in collaboration with the Aviation Twin Transition Cluster.

Figure 2 Projects and initiatives that have joined the AIRSHIP clustering events by M24

3.4 Dissemination results and next steps

As per the Key Performance Indicators set out in the Grant Agreement, the results for publications, events and clustering are well on track to be achieved by the end of the project

Table 4 KPIs for dissemination

Actions	KPI	Current
Peer reviewed publications	10 open access papers	2+2
Organization and participation in scientific and industrial conferences, workshops, etc	30 events	10
Clustering events	4 clustering events / 20 related projects and initiatives	2 events/ 11 projects and initiatives

During the upcoming months, the dissemination of the project will focus on intensifying the participation in scientific and industrial conferences, as well as joining planned workshops already in planning by the projects and initiatives that AIRSHIP is clustering with. The peer-reviewed publications and public deliverables, as well as other publishable outputs (such as tutorials) will be uploaded to Zenodo – the EU Open Research Repository.

4 Exploitation

Exploitation in the AIRSHIP project is defined as the actions taken to increase the uptake of any result and output of the project that could lead to further research, innovation, commercialization or solutions.

The exploitation strategy for the AIRSHIP project is comprised of three objectives:

- 1- Creating and marketing the AIRSHIP models either commercially or through Open licenses to third parties interested in picking up the work.
- 2- Further development and tailoring of the models developed in AIRSHIP under future joint research activities under national and European programmes.
- 3- Use of results by the research community

The current efforts of the WP9 leaders are focused on the third objective, and, as such, the first step has been identifying the Key Exploitable Results at this point of the project.

4.1 First exploitation workshop

During the third Consortium Meeting, the partners participated in the first exploitation workshop, which was organised under the wings of the first innovation inventory workshop. The main objectives of this workshop were to identify possible Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that could be considered for exploitation at this point at their current state-of-the-art, and to ensure that the WP leaders had all the necessary information for the exploitation plan for each of the KERs identified.

In order to achieve this, the leaders of WP9 organised an activity on Unique Value Propositions, in which each WP leader filled out the template with the result that they considered had the most potential at their current state.

Figure 3 Example of a Unique Value Proposition template

4.2 Exploitation results and next steps

As a result of the exploitation workshop, 9 Key Exploitable Results (KERs) -not counting the AIRSHIP models- have been identified and are being analysed in order to create exploitation plan proposals for the ones that are the most likely to succeed. At this point, the immediate steps being considered are the inclusion of the KERs in the Horizon Results Platform and for the project to participate in the Horizon Results Booster.

Before this can be advanced, though, a second exploitation workshop will set IPR and ownership expectations on the results and will ensure the agreement of all partners to the future actions. Furthermore, a subpage on the website will be dedicate to the outputs and results of the project once identified.

At the moment of writing this deliverable, the Consortium is preparing a proposal for a workshop for the European Maritime Days in May 2025 in Cork, Ireland. The workshop will be focused on market acceptance and regulatory compliance of unmanned vehicles in maritime transport and will encompass activities related to Task 9.1 and Task 9.3.

5 Communication

The following tools and channels were set up at the start of the project and have been consistently used to bring awareness of the project and its advances to all the target audiences described in Deliverables 9.1, that is general public, primary and secondary school students, STEM students and stakeholders.

5.1 Project image

The project image consists of all the graphic elements that make up the visual identity of AIRSHIP: logo, colour schemes and fonts.

During the kick-off meeting, the visual identity of the project including the version 1 of the AIRSHIP logo, as well as the templates for presentations, documents and deliverables were implemented already during the meeting.

The first logo of the project was delivered in M1 and presented at the kick-off meeting. The first version of the logo (Figure 4) depicted the initial shape of the prototype.

Figure 4 AIRSHIP logo - version 1

As the project advanced, the new prototypes were developing the present shape of the AOS-1. Consequently, during the M12 Consortium Meeting, the consortium agrees to changing the logo accordingly. This new logo (Figure 5) is thus implemented in all the tools available by M13.

Figure 5 AIRSHIP logo - version 2

The project image also included in the presentation template, in the document template and in the deliverables template, as well as the in first project poster and brochure. The poster, brochure and logo are available at the website in the [Media Kit section](#).

5.2 Website

The AIRSHIP website is published in M04. Wordpress is the web content management system chosen for publication and maintenance of the AIRSHIP website, which is written and updated in PHP. It is hosted in

GoDaddy and the chosen url is www.airshipproject.eu.

It is designed following the project identity over the Enfold template and with the Elementor 3.24 theme builder.

Dynamic and modern visuals are prioritized, using first the animations created for the social media campaign of the project until M12 and going forward the most update real-life footage of the field test of the models.

5.2.1 Structure

The menu of the website is comprised of:

- Home page: designed to give a brief overview of the project, the team and its objectives, it also contains direct links to the latest news and the sign up option to the website.

Figure 6 Main page of the AIRSHIP webpage (www.airshipproject.eu)

- About us: detailed information about the Consortium and individual roles and responsibilities within AIRSHIP as well as the introduction of the Advisory Board.
- News and events: Space to publish the latest news relevant to the project and information about future and past events where the AIRSHIP consortium was present.
- The Project: a more exhaustive description of the components of the project, its objectives and expected outcomes, as well as a clear overview of the state-of-the-art of the technologies being developed. The Features and Showcase subpages were co-created alongside the technical partners and are routinely reviewed and updated, as explained in point 2.2.2. Consortium Input of this report.
- Resources: a short overview of the Work Packages and tasks of the project is presented in order to offer a clear view of the process of the project. All printable and reusable graphic materials created for the dissemination of the project are uploaded to the Media Kit page, while videos and photos of the consortium and the work on the technologies are uploaded to the Gallery.

Figure 7 AIRSHIP's website menu dropdown

5.2.2 Consortium Input

As previously mentioned, the Consortium, and specially the technical partners, are consulted about the publications and information contained in the website. This two-way communication is crucial to ensure the veracity of the information, as well as highlighting the most relevant, up-to-date and attractive information about the work being undertaken.

The website is presented to the whole Consortium every Consortium Meeting and to the technical partners whenever their input is needed or there are new publications in need of review during the bi-weekly technical meetings.

5.2.3 Results

As previously mentioned, the AIRSHIP website (www.airshipproject.eu) was planned, designed and launched before M04 of the project. The measurement of visits, views and engagement is done through the Statistics plugin, installed in M04 alongside the publication of the website.

The KPI described in the Grant Agreement was 2.000 visitors by M12 and a minimum of 6.000 visitors by end of project (M60). At M23 the website has surpassed the 6.000 individual visitors and is on its way to achieve 24.000 visits to the different pages, ensuring and surpassing the expected KPIs even before the exploitation efforts have truly begun.

5.2.4 Planned updated

For the upcoming second half of the project an update of the website is planned in order to face the exploitation phase of the project, showcase the new models and highlight the clustering, technology roadmap and planned technical workshops to the interested stakeholders.

As part of this intensification of the media campaign, the following pages are planned:

- Update and upload of all new publications
- Technical tutorials page
- Key Exploitable Results subpages
- Creation and publication of a project Ebook

5.3 Social Media

The AIRSHIP project's social media strategy is focused on X and LinkedIn, even though Facebook, Instagram and YouTube were also set up in M01 of the project. The main objective of the posts up to this point has been promoting the events the project has been presented in and achieving wider visibility. The handle for all social media accounts is @airship_project.

5.3.1 X

The link to the AIRSHIP X is www.x.com/Airship_Project . Even though the number of followers is still low (57 followers), the analytics show good impressions and healthy engagement.

Figure 8 AIRSHIP's X best performing post and general analytics

5.3.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is, as was expected, the most successful social media channel with 261 followers and the one in which most of the effort is spent.

Followers are steady in growth, the posting is frequent and both the demographics and impressions are relevant and in line with the objectives of the project.

Figure 9 AIRSHIP's LinkedIn and X followers demographics breakdown

Highlights

Data for 12/3/2023 - 12/1/2024

46,091 Impressions	891 Reactions	6 Comments	16 Reposts
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Visitor highlights

1,285 Page views	418 Unique visitors
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Figure 10 AIRSHIP's LinkedIn analytics

5.3.3 Planned strategy for social media

For the second part of the project (M24-M48) the focus will be on achieving the KPIs set out in the Grant Agreement. Towards this objective, several video campaigns, paid advertisement and collaboration with other projects and relevant initiatives -such as Refmap's project Aviation Twin Transition Cluster- will be carried out.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, the target is to have 1.000 social media followers across all platforms by M48. At M24 we count with 325 total followers, though it is envisioned to achieve the KPI as more relevant materials are published and the collaboration with other projects is materialised.

5.4 Communication materials

Following the project stylebook, a set of communication materials to present the project and inform of the development of the actions have been prepared and updated as needed. Further updates and materials are planned as the project develops.

5.4.1 Graphic materials

The first and second sets of graphic materials are the project's banners, posters, rollups, video and brochures, which are all available in [the website's media kit](#).

Figure 11 AIRSHIP's posters versions 1, 2 and 3.

The poster and brochure are also translated to Spanish and Portuguese and the editable versions are available to all partners for their translation and printing.

A communication package was set at the beginning of the project, including:

- An AIRSHIP promotional video
- A general presentation of the project
- The rollup of the project
- The poster of the project
- A brochure

A full update of all materials and the package is planned for M30, orientating the content towards exploitation and updating the information on the technology.

5.4.2 Newsletters

The AIRSHIP newsletter, including news about the project and associated clustering activities, is managed through the MailChimp email marketing platform. The AIRSHIP website also includes a form, so that interested parties can also sign up to receive the project newsletter, which has also been promoted via social media.

So far, there has been two editions of the newsletter -third one coming this M24-, which are also published in the website:

[AIRSHIP Newsletter January-June 2023](#)

[AIRSHIP Newsletter July 2024](#)

The results so far are not encouraging, as newsletters seem to be phasing out generally in most projects: 26 subscribers, and a total of 117 visits to the newsletters pages on the website. Moving forward, a change of format towards an ebulletin published on the website and social media might be recommended in order to achieve the KPI of a 1.000 stakeholders reached by the end of the project.

5.4.3 Videos

A [promotional video](#) of the project was prepared in M06 and updated in M12. It was published in YouTube and the website and has been used to promote AIRSHIP in several events.

The update of the video contained recordings from the A0-S maiden test flight in the Inari Lake in Finland, which are also published in the project's YouTube channel.

During the II Consortium Meeting, [a series of interviews to the female researchers of AIRSHIP](#) were conducted and published as part of the 11-F campaign (UNESCO Day of Women and Girls in Science) highlighting the gender dimension aspect of the project.

5.5 Other communication activities

On top of the utilisation of the previously presented tools and channels, the AIRSHIP project has also undertaken other activities beneficial to the awareness raising of the activities.

5.5.1 Press conference and press releases

A joint press conference during the opening of the CIAG (Blue Innovation Center of Granadilla) was organised, in which all project partners presented the project alongside the directive team of CIAG, the dean of the University of La Laguna, the director of the Ocean Platform of the Canary Islands and the President of the Cabildo. During the press conference and consecutive press releases, the benefits for the Canary Islands and the use of the AIRSHIP for quick transport of goods were highlighted.

Figure 12 Pictures of the CIAG joint press conference

Further press releases and conferences are planned. Contacts with the Research*EU and Horizon Magazine, as well as with Euronews and other EU-wide media channels are already underway preparing for the final phases of the project.

5.5.2 Communication events and initiatives

AIRSHIP has been presented in the EU Corner of the European Researchers' Night of the Macaronesia (MACARONIGHT IV and V) in 2023 and 2024 in the islands of Tenerife and Gran Canaria, receiving an estimate of 2.000 high school students per edition.

The interview series of the female researchers working on AIRSHIP is part of the 11-F and Chic@s con Ciencia initiatives, being projected around high schools in Spain and Portugal.

Figure 13 AIRSHIP in the EU Corner of the European Researchers Night of the Macaronesia

5.6 Communication results

The AIRSHIP project communication activities, tools and channels are closely monitored and coordinated by the WP9 leader to keep track of all on-going activities in this task (T9.1). In order to measure the impact of the previously described activities and channels and to be able to adjust the strategy if need be in order to achieve the expected outcomes and maximising visibility, a set of metrics were developed and presented in the proposal and the Grant Agreement. Such metrics allow having a constant view of the amount and the effectiveness of the communication activities conducted.

The table below presents the state-of-the-art of the AIRSHIP communications Key Performance Indicators by Month 24 as stated in the Grant Agreement.

Table 5 Communiation Key Performance Indicators

Actions	KPI	Current (M24)
Website (www.airshipproject.eu)	2000 visitors by M12 6000 visitors by M60	6184 visitors
Social Media (LinkedIn, Youtube and Twitter)	1000 followers in all social media channels by M60	325 followers
Promotional videos	3 videos	2 animation videos (and a set of six interviews)
Newsletters	1000 stakeholders reached	> 150 views
Technical seminars and tutorials	6 technical tutorials / seminars	0 – In progress for the upcoming year

